

Einstein's Clock Experiment

Didier François Viel

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email : arcopodias@gmail.com

1 Abstract

« Imagination is more important than knowledge ».
Albert Einstein.

The Einstein clock on a train refers to a thought experiment done by Einstein when he was elaborating his SR relativity theory. This thought experiment consists of a light beam reflecting back and forth between two parallel mirrors, acting like a clock, and being on a moving train. The speed of the light ray, viewed by two observers, one from the embankment and the other one on the moving train, is the basis of the thought experiment. From this experiment, Einstein deduced that time and space are not absolute in the universe and depend on the velocity of the observer. We will show that the conclusion about this experiment depends on the way the light beam propagates with respect to the two observers and demonstrate why Einstein is wrong.

2 Description of the Experiment

The starting point of this thought is the affirmation that “The laws of physics are the same in all inertial frames of reference”. Which turns into “All experiments run the same in all inertial frames of reference”. At that time, the model for light propagation was Maxwell's wave electromagnetic model. Arago showed that light is propagating at the same speed in a medium (the nature of which nobody knows) whatever the speed of the source or the observer [1]. With this fact, Einstein stated that the speed of light was a constant in every inertial frame of reference. This constancy can be proved with certain hypothesis [2].

Also the true nature of light was unknown and only the wave behavior was thought to exist. We will see in the following that the trajectory of the light path inside the clock on the train was supposed by Einstein as a straight vertical line, the light bouncing back and forth, up and down. It means clearly that in his thought experiment, Einstein considered the propagation of the wavelike behavior of the light beam in the atmospheric air of the train, as if the light was entrained by it (we will see the physical complexity of light propagation later).

If we analyze Einstein's thought experiment, it is said that the observer on the embankment can see the light beam going from mirror to mirror. He records the impact points of the light beam on the mirrors in his own reference frame and trace the light path in it. The observer on the train does the same thing.

For the observer on the train the light beam is propagating back and forth from the lower mirror to the upper mirror, supposed to be in a stable vertical straight line (from Einstein's hypothesis). For the observer on the embankment, it is obvious that he is viewing the light path in the train as a triangle, starting from the source, reflecting to the upper mirror and going back down on the lower mirror some distance away from the source.

This thought experiment is often illustrated by replacing the light beam by a ball bouncing back and forth between the two mirrors. Doing that, we can show that the trajectories of the ball, traced in the two reference frames are the same as the light clock experiment. A triangle for the observer on the embankment and a straight line for the observer on the train. We know that the bouncing ball will go up and down vertically at the same speed in both reference frames, but the trajectory seen from the embankment is a triangle. This triangle trajectory of the ball seen from the embankment can be explained by the fact that the ball is also moving with the train velocity, since the ball is entrained by the ambient air in the train. In the ball thought experiment, there is no surprise, Galilean physics is respected.

3 Einstein Interpretation

For the light beam emitted by the source on the train, Einstein said that this way of thinking for the ball is not valid for the light clock experiment since he stated that:

- the hypotenuse of the triangle is the “real” trajectory of the light beam seen from the embankment, meaning that the light beam “really” propagates in the reference embankment frame,
- the speed of light is a constant in all reference frames.

With these two assumptions, Einstein said that time and space are not the same for the two observers in relative motion to explain this thought experiment [3].

Why is that? If the real trajectory of the light beam seen from the embankment is the hypotenuse of the triangle and if the speed of light is the same in all reference frames, then there is something wrong. Indeed, the light beam seems to go faster when seen from the embankment. This is impossible, except if space and time can change with the observer velocity! This is Einstein’s reasoning and he derives a transformation of the space-time coordinates which explains this strange behavior of the light clock in a train.

4 Analysis

Einstein is right if what the observer on the embankment sees is a “real physical path” of the light beam in his own reference frame. Is it? No, the light beam is not propagating in the ambient air of the embankment but in the ambient air moving with the train. There is no physical connections between the air in the moving train and the air of the embankment, proving that the light is not propagating in the air of the embankment.

More importantly, why the light beam on the train can propagate vertically with respect to the observer on the moving train?

To answer to this question, of what the “real physical” light path in the ambient air on the train is, we, at the start, have to agree of the physical nature of the propagating medium. Is it, as Maxwell supposed, a medium called “ether”, static in the universe, which embeded all matter? If we take these above hypothesis, it is shown that light is entrained by the air atoms constituents’ velocity, but only partly [4]. In this reference, it is explained how light is propagating in a medium like air and that the light is getting part of the velocity of the moving medium, with respect to the vacuum (ether) supposed static. It is obvious that Einstein never, never, imagined such hypothesis for the light propagation. Moreover, to respect Einstein thought experiment, the light going up and down on a straight vertical path, we have to consider here that light is totally entrained by the moving ambient air in the train.

Since the light beam is not propagating in the embankment air, what the observer on the embankment is seeing, is a “virtual light path”, as we know it is the case in the ball example, entrained by the moving train due to the entrainment by the ambient air and bouncing back and forth vertically between the two mirrors. For light, this virtual triangle path is built by addition of the train velocity vector to the light velocity vector with velocity is equal to the speed c on the vertical path and not on the hypotenuse!

We can conclude from the above demonstration, that Einstein's thought experiment is wrong due to its wrong assumptions about light propagation, which are not physically supported, and then erroneous for its conclusions.

Recalling that "All experiments run the same in all inertial frames of reference", there remains a question: can this clock experiment done on the train be done in the same way in the reference frame of the embankment?

Surely, the observer on the embankment can do it the same way in his reference frame. The ambient air constitution can be made the same as in the train, and the same hypothesis about the propagation in the still ambient air of the embankment can be made. The light will go up and down in the same condition since the air and the clocks are the same. If we neglect the entrainment of the light due to the motion of the earth relative to the static ether (500 km/s!), then the trajectory will be simply a vertical straight line as in the train, with the same length. He will get the same pulse rate as the observer on the train.

In conclusion, the observer on the embankment can do the same clock experiment as the one done on the train and he gets the same result! He can conclude that time and space are not relative to each other. Then, how does Einstein get to his false conclusions? Because he permits the observer on the embankment to look at the light propagating in the air clock on the train, thinking that it is propagating in his own reference frame. It is false to say that this light beam is propagating in the air of the embankment, and in consequence it is false to say that time and space are relative.

5 Conclusion

It can be emphasized that the hypothesis of Einstein's thought experiment are very simplistic. They are ignoring the physical reality of the (as yet-unknown) propagating medium, the unknown dual nature of light at the time, the omission of the refraction effect in a moving medium, the velocity of earth in space, etc.

Even not being part of the Academic world of physics, we have the right to say that this thought experiment is non sense. It is not entirely the fault of Einstein himself, since knowledge about light propagation was deficient at the time. Nevertheless, it is unfortunate that this kind of thought experiment leads to the SR theory which is untrue. After that, this theory was enhanced to explain the gravitation force. Based on this latter theory, the Big Bang theory was developed, and now the James Web telescope is demonstrating a Big Mistake. This should open the eyes of the Academic community to abandon Einstein's SR and GR theories.

References

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